

RF Electromagnetic Fields Exposure Monitoring using Drive Test and Sensors in a French City

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Abstract

This paper presents the monitoring work on radio-frequency (RF) electromagnetic field (EMF) exposure, carried out in a French city by using drive test and sensor network methods. The drive test measurements are realized by continuously measuring in a car via a portable spectrum analyzer, i.e., Tektronix RSA 306B, connected to a 3-axis antenna. It records electric (E) field values over a broad cellular band (700 MHz – 3.8 GHz) along the pre-defined outdoor routes at a height of 2 meters above the soil level. Secondly, a total of 19 sensors are installed near the center of the city, on the streetlamps (4 meters to the soil), which measure the broad band (250 kHz – 6 GHz) exposure level. The statistical distribution of measurement data is analyzed, and compared with base station antenna (BSA) information, which can be publicly accessed. Furthermore, the temporal variation of measurements collected by sensor networks is analyzed.

1 Introduction

With the development in wireless networks, the public concern on potential risk of electromagnetic field (EMF) exposure is gaining more and more attention. To respond to the public and for the compliance purpose, long-term massive radio-frequency (RF) EMF monitoring campaigns have been carried out internationally for years [1–4].

The monitoring works of downlink (DL) RF-EMF exposure are done by 3 types measurement methods, i.e., spot measurements, sensor networks, and drive test measurements. Spot measurements are usually carried out by accredited laboratories, e.g., ANFR [5] in France and EEAE in Greece [6]. Sensor networks have been installed in several European cities since the beginning of 21st century. However, the spot and sensor measurements require a large amount of investment in money and time. Therefore, drive test measurement is becoming more popular in the past decade. It can be done within a few hours and covers significantly long distance, such as 10 km in a medium size city, which provides us the large-scale RF-EMF exposure map spatially.

In France, both sensor networks and drive test measurement campaigns start in 2019, [7, 8]. Here in the present paper, we focus on the measurement data collected from the sensors installed in Massy since April 2022, and data collected from drive test measurements in January 2023. We first explain the measurements system for both drive test and sensor networks, where both systems are able to monitor RF-EMF exposure from all cellular bands. Then, the statistical distributions of collected data are analyzed, the spatial electric (E) field values (from all DL cellular bands) are compared with density of nearby base station antenna (BSA) sources, where BSA information is obtained from open-accessed website [9]. On the other hand, the autonomous sensor networks record broadband E field level every two hours. The daily temporal variations from different sensors show the same trend from night to day. The mean values of sensor measurements also show inverse-proportional relationships with the distances to the nearest BSA.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 and Section 3 introduce the system setup for drive test measurements and sensor networks. Section 4 presents the analysis on collected data. Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Drive Test Measurement Setup

The drive test measurements are carried out in a French city, i.e., Massy, using a portable spectrum analyzer, i.e., RSA306B from Tektronix. A wide frequency band from 700 to 3800 MHz was selected. The Tektronix RSA 306B is connected to 3-axis dipole antenna via a switch controlled by Arduino. The isotropic measurements are obtained by combining the root mean square (RMS) value from each axis. In the measurement setup, the 3-axis antenna was fixed on the top of the vehicle while the rest of the measurements system stays inside the car.

The drive test route shown in Figure 2, includes a total itinerary of 16.3 km, done in 50 min. The average driving speed is 20 km/h. For the considered 700 to 3800 MHz band, the RSA306B system records one complete 3-axis measurement within 0.8 s. Therefore, the average distance between two successive measurement points is around 4.4 m.

3 RF-EMF Exposure Sensor Networks

Figure 1. EMF Sensor installed on streetlamps and the sensor networks map in Massy.

In this section, we introduce the sensor network system, deployed in French cities. The broadband sensors designed by EXEM [10] are usually installed in urban city environments. As shown in Figure 1, each sensor is composed of three orthogonal E field probes connected to diode detectors, an acquisition system, a wireless communication system (sigfox) and batteries, which are optimized to achieve 4 years of autonomy. They are deployed at a height of 4 m, preferably on the street lamps. The 3-axis broadband sensor measures the spatial components of the E field in the range (250 kHz - 6 GHz). Every 2 hours, the sensor is activated to conduct one measurement, which lasts for 6 min in total, to achieve a stable performance in E field strength. We have 19 such kind of sensors installed in Massy since April 2022.

4 Results

In this section, the statistical analysis on data collected from drive test measurements and sensor networks is provided. Furthermore, the spatial correlation between outdoor RF-EMF exposure level and BSA information are explored. The temporal variation recorded from the sensor network is analyzed as well.

4.1 Drive Test Measurements

In Figure 2, the drive test routes are selected to cover main outdoor facilities, including a train station, commercial centers, residential area, and office buildings. The black dots indicate the locations of BSA, where each BSA site can have several antennas covering cellular frequency bands from different operators.

Figure 2. Drive test measurement routes and RF-EMF exposure map, where colorbar indicates measured E field level in V/m.

The raw spectrum from broadband measurement data is stored instantly in the drive test. Then in the post-processing, only downlink (DL) cellular bands are selected. The total DL RF-EMF exposure is calculated based on RMS values from all DL bands. The average total E field level recorded from drive test is 0.58 V/m with standard deviation (std) 0.59 V/m. The maximum value recorded is 5.8 V/m. For measurement points near to the BSA, there is higher possibility of experiencing higher exposure level, although it also depends on the local environments near the receiving probe.

Since the drive test measurements record instantaneous E field values along the route, data are significantly disturbed by random noise. Therefore, we performed a moving average method over a sliding window, to remove the noise. In Figure 3, the sliding window size is set to be 100 m to 300 m. With a bigger window size, the curves are smoother while more variations are removed. Note that we should not consider very large sliding window sizes in order to avoid removing the desired variation. Since the unwanted noisy variation follow normal distribution due to the noisy nature of the data. So, we performed the Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) test to check the appropriate size of sliding window and consequently only smooth the noise level.

Figure 3. Moving average using different sliding window size

In Figure 4, we present the results of KS tests for five considered sliding window sizes. For each sliding window size, we apply the KS test for all data belonging to the window, and check if the data falls into normal distribution. If it is close to normal distribution, the p-value given by the KS test, will be higher than 0.05, which means that the null hypothesis should not be rejected. The cumulative distribution function (CDF) plots show that, with a smaller window size, most of the p-values from all windowed fragments are higher than 0.05, which indicates higher probability to be normally distributed. It also verifies the motivation of adopting a moving average to remove the randomness. Comparing sliding window size, measurement data inside a window size of $\pm 100\text{m}$ has around 70% probability to be normal-distributed. For size of $\{\pm 200\text{m}, \pm 250\text{m}, \pm 300\text{m}\}$, only around 20%-30% can be considered as normal-distributed. Therefore, we adopt the sliding window of 100m in this work.

Figure 4. KS test for data inside one sliding window

After the moving average method is applied. The correlation between E field in drive test and BSA information is analyzed. The correlation coefficient is 0.62 between smoothed E Field and BSA density. Here the BSA density is calculated as mean number of BSA inside a circle centered at each measurement point with radius R ($R=250\text{m}$). It should be noted that all BSA at each physical site are taken into consideration, including all active bands. The results show a considerable correlation between E field values and nearby BSA density.

4.2 Sensor Networks

The sensor networks deployed in the urban area of a French city, capture the hourly variation of E field exposure. We analyzed the mean value and std from all sensors. The averaging duration for each sensor is different, since 15 out of 19 sensors are installed in April 2022, while the rest are deployed in January 2023. From Figure 5, we observe that most sensors measure a quite low level of RF-EMF exposure, around 0.5 V/m. The distance to the nearest physical BS site is also plotted in the figure. It should be noted that two of them stand out, i.e., 04 & 16, since they are in the line-of-sight (LoS) and main beam direction of nearby active BSA. The distance to nearest BS can explain partially

Figure 5. Mean values from all sensors installed in Massy, considering a total duration of 10 months.

the reason why E Field level is high or low. However, the main beam direction of antenna, number of active antennas at one site, and surrounding environments near the sensor also play very important roles.

For the sensors that record a mean value higher than 0.5V/m, we performed the temporal variation analysis. In Figure 6, the scaled temporal variation is provided. Each sensor measurement is scaled with its mean and then averaged over 24 hours. It can be seen that all sensors exhibit a clear decrease at night then increase in E field level during the day.

Figure 6. Scaled temporal variation from sensor networks with significant E field level.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we present the RF-EMF exposure monitoring works carried out in France. The drive test measurements and sensors measurements are done in a French city, covering all DL cellular frequency bands. The drive test measurements are realized by continuously measuring in a car via a portable spectrum analyzer with a 3-axis antenna.

The 19 sensors are installed on the streetlamps, which measure broad band (250 kHz – 6 GHz) exposure. The statistical distribution of drive test measurements show significant spatial variation along the whole driving distance of 16 km, where local measurements within 100 meters show a normal-like distribution. After performing the moving average to smooth measurement data, the correlation between E field values and nearby BSA density is analyzed, where a considerable correlation is shown. The same conclusion can be drawn from sensor measurements, where higher mean values of E field are usually found in the sensors within short distance to nearby BSA. However, the distance and density of BSA are not the only factors that influence the RF-EMF exposure levels, other factors, such as, the directions and number of active antennas, the traffic load, and surrounding environments, are important as well.

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